

1 **PKC isoforms function at the cell membrane to facilitate completion of cell division in**
2 **transformation.**

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7 Protein kinase C isoforms act at the cell membrane during cytokinesis with molecules including RhoA and
8 ECT2 to complete cell division. We studied whole transcription in human solid tumors and discovered
9 biased activation of the iota isoform of PRKC, PRKCI. In breast cancer, PRKCI was a defining element of
10 the tumor gene signature, while PRKCA and PRKCZ were not. In human cervical cancer, PRKCI, PRKCZ
11 and PRKCA were activated, while PRKCQ, PRKCB and PRKCE were silenced or not affected. In early
12 transformation in the vulva (vulva epithelial neoplasia, or VIN), PRKCI and PRKCA were activated while
13 PRKCE was suppressed and PRKCZ was unaffected. PRKCI and PRKCA but not PRKCE, PRKCZ or
14 PRKCA were identified blindly and at the transcriptome level across multiple settings as co-regulated gene
15 products of ECT2 and RhoA, together suggesting the PRKCI isoform was selectively associated with
16 transformed cellular contexts. Depletion of PRKCI in lung cancer cells *in vitro* resulted in reduction of
17 proliferation evidenced by down-regulation of *EZH2* and *MKI67*, alterations in cell cycling and spindle
18 dynamics marked by reduction in *CDK4* and *E2F2*, *TPX2*, and kinesin *Kif23* and changes in asymmetric
19 cells division bias indicated by loss of *POC1A* expression with activation of *RMND5A*. Defects in
20 cytokinesis were evidenced by silencing of *ANLN* and *CEP55*, suppression of myosin light chain kinase
21 *MYLK* and reduction in *ROCK1* expression. PROCI functions at the cell membrane with ECT2 and RHOA
22 to facilitate completion of the cell cycle during cytokinesis, is activated in solid tumors in humans and its
23 depletion results in global dysfunction in cycling.
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